

Synthesis and Structural Studies of a New Series of Bimetallic Complexes with Nitrogen or Oxygen Donor Ligands

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The metal cyanates, $M(NCO)_2$, where $M = Co^{II}$ or Ni^{II} , react with $Tl_2(SCN)_2$ to form addition compounds of the type $M(NCO)_2Tl_2(SCN)_2$. These compounds behave as Lewis acid and form complexes with certain ligands (L), viz tetrahydrofuran (thf), dimethylsulphoxide (dmsO), methanol (MeOH), nicotinamide (nia), pyridine (py), 2,2-bipyridyl (bipy) and 1,10-phenanthroline (phen). These complexes are characterised by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic moment electronic and infrared spectral studies. The nature of bonding has been related to the quantitative softness parameters of metals and ligands, and the proposed structures are also supported by Pearson's HSAB principles.

A number of tetrathiocyanate and selenocyanate of the type $MM'(XCN)_4$, where $X=S$ or Se , have been synthesised. The cyanate ion also possesses two potential donor site, i.e. N and O end. The established bonding modes for this ion is through N-end ($M-NCO$), O-end ($M-OCN$) or bridged ($M-NCO-M$)¹. In the present paper we report the synthesis and structural studies of dicyanato-dithiocyanate complexes and their adducts with various nitrogen or oxygen donor ligands in order to study the bonding modes of cyanate and thiocyanate ions in these complexes.

Experimental

Reagent grade metal nitrates, potassium thiocyanate (AnalaR) and potassium cyanate (E. Merck) were used as such. Ligands and solvents were used after purification by known methods. $TlSCN$ was prepared by the reported method².

Preparation of $M(NCO)_2Tl_2(SCN)_2$; where $M=Co^{II}$ or Ni^{II} : A solution of metal cyanate, $M(NCO)_2$ (1 mmol) were prepared in dry alcohol by stirring metal nitrate (1 mmol) and $KNCO$ (2 mmol) overnight. The precipitated KNO_3 was filtered off. To the coloured filtrate, $TlSCN$ (<2 mmol) was added and stirred for ~36 h. The product formed was filtered, washed with solvent and dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum.

Preparation of $M(NCO)_2Tl_2(SCN)_2 \cdot xL$; where x is 2 for $L=thf, MeOH, dmsO, acetone$, 6 for $L=py, nia$, 3 for $L=bipy, phen$, $M(NCO)_2Tl_2(SCN)_2 \cdot 6py$: To a suspension of $M(NCO)_2Tl_2(SCN)_2$ (1 mmol) in ethanol (30 ml), a solution of pyridine (6 mmol) in ethanol was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for ~24 h. The pink solid complexes were

formed in case of cobalt while green solid product formed in case of nickel. Each solid was separated, washed with solvent and dried in vacuum over P_2O_5 . All other complexes were similarly prepared. Alternatively, the thf, dmsO and methanol complexes could also be prepared by taking these as solvents in place of ethanol.

Analysis of complexes: All the complexes were analysed as described elsewhere², and gave satisfactory analytical results. The analytical data are presented in Table 1.

Physical measurements: All complexes decomposed without melting and dissolved to some extent in dimethylformamide. The physical measurements were carried out as earlier².

Results and Discussion

$M(NCO)_2Tl_2(SCN)_2$, where $M=Co^{II}$ or Ni^{II} : On reaction with metal cyanate, $M(NCO)_2$, the $Tl_2(SCN)_2$ form complexes of general formula $M(NCO)_2Tl_2(SCN)_2$. These compounds have been referred to as Lewis acid due to unsaturation coordination number of $M(II)$. The molar conductance values show that they are non-conducting in nature.

The ir spectra indicate that ν_{CN} , ν_{CS} and δ_{NOS} bands appeared in the ranges 2130-150, 780-785 and 465-475 cm^{-1} , respectively, indicating the presence of only bridged thiocyanate groups³. Since the thiocyanates are bridged, it can be believed on the basis of Pearson HSAB principles that $M(II)$ being harder will link to harder N-end, and $Tl(I)$ being softer, will link to softer S-end of thiocyanate. Further, these complexes exhibit a strong to medium band at 2260-230 cm^{-1} due to

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % · Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.	Molar conductance $\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$
			N	Co/Ni	Tl	S		
$\text{Co}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Blue	190	8.08 (8.39)	8.98 (8.84)	61.00 (61.16)	9.32 (9.59)	4.40	30.50
$(\text{MeOH})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Pink	185	7.23 (7.66)	8.01 (8.07)	55.72 (55.81)	8.40 (8.75)	5.08	41.20
$(\text{Acetone})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Pink	158	6.96 (7.15)	7.21 (7.53)	51.96 (52.10)	8.01 (8.17)	5.02	40.21
$(\text{dmsO})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Pink	176	6.30 (6.80)	6.80 (7.16)	49.12 (49.57)	15.21 (15.55)	5.11	38.70
$(\text{thf})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Pink	168	7.01 (6.90)	7.30 (7.27)	49.80 (50.30)	7.56 (7.89)	5.13	40.10
$(\text{py})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Pink	160	12.02 (12.24)	4.95 (5.16)	35.27 (35.69)	5.45 (5.59)	4.92	125.40
$(\text{nia})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Pink	172	15.94 (16.01)	3.90 (4.21)	28.90 (29.16)	4.42 (4.57)	4.98	122.20
$(\text{bipy})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Pink	188	11.97 (12.33)	4.88 (5.19)	35.50 (35.94)	5.54 (5.63)	5.10	126.18
$(\text{phen})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Brown	165	10.88 (11.10)	4.32 (4.67)	32.21 (32.35)	5.07 (5.10)	4.96	124.25
$\text{Ni}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Green	175	8.20 (8.40)	8.50 (8.70)	61.10 (61.26)	9.50 (9.60)	3.00	35.50
$(\text{MeOH})_2\text{Ni}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Light green	211	7.20 (7.67)	7.52 (7.94)	55.65 (55.89)	8.66 (8.76)	3.04	40.12
$(\text{thf})_2\text{Ni}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Green	202	6.80 (6.91)	7.06 (7.1)	50.21 (50.37)	7.50 (7.90)	3.02	45.12
$(\text{py})_2\text{Ni}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Green	208	11.94 (12.25)	4.94 (5.07)	35.40 (35.72)	5.48 (5.60)	2.96	120.26
$(\text{nia})_2\text{Ni}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Green	210	15.80 (16.02)	3.90 (4.10)	28.86 (29.18)	4.46 (4.57)	2.98	120.10
$(\text{bipy})_2\text{Ni}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Green	180	11.88 (12.34)	4.95 (5.11)	35.80 (35.97)	5.60 (5.64)	3.24	122.80
$(\text{phen})_2\text{Ni}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Green	182	11.10 (11.11)	4.45 (4.60)	32.00 (32.38)	4.98 (5.07)	3.16	126.22

ν_{CN} of cyanate group. The position of bands due to ν_{CO} and δ_{NCO} appeared at 1300–1280 as a weak band and 635–670 cm^{-1} , respectively. These data closely resemble the ir data for end-to-end cyanate bridge ($-\text{NCO}-$)^{1,4,5}.

The electronic spectra of cobalt Lewis acid show the presence of two intense bands due to d-d transitions which are assigned to ${}^4\text{A}_2 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{P})$ (ν_3) and ${}^4\text{A}_2 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{F})$ (ν_2), respectively. The electronic spectral data and magnetic moment values (Table 1) indicate that cobalt is in tetrahedral geometry in these complexes. While in case of nickel Lewis acids, three bands are observed which are assigned to ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ (ν_3), ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$ (ν_2) and ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$ (ν_1), respectively. These data indicate the presence of octahedral geometry around Ni^{2+} . The octahedral geometry of Ni^{2+} is perhaps acquired by axial coordination of other molecule of adjacent layer⁶. On the basis of the above results, the polymeric bridged structure may be proposed (Charts 1 and 2). The

Chart 1

Chart 2

proposed structure is further supported by the following points: (i) thallium prefers linear structure like AgSCN^7 , and (ii) the bands observed in the region 300–295 cm^{-1} is due to $\nu_{\text{M-NCS}}$ bending.

Adducts: In $\text{M}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$, the coordination number of cobalt is four against the maximum of six, while nickel prefers effective coordination number of six. Accordingly, these have been treated with a number of Lewis bases. The complexes obtained have been divided into two groups and discussed.

Bridged complexes: $(L_2)\text{M}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$, where $L = \text{MeOH}, \text{thf}, \text{dmsO}, \text{acetone}$: These bases form adducts of general formula $(L_2)\text{M}(\text{NCO})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{SCN})_2$, which is evident from the band observed in the region 270–245 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{M-L}}$ frequency.

The ir spectra of these adducts show that there is no significant change in the positions of ν_{ON} , ν_{CS} and δ_{NCS} due to thiocyanate groups, and ν_{ON} , ν_{OO} and δ_{NCO} of cyanate group on adduct formation. There is, however, a negative shift in the position of ν_{M-NCS} when M is cobalt. This change in ν_{M-NCS} is on account of change in geometry of the metal ion from tetrahedral to octahedral. It has earlier been observed that a change in geometry causes a negative shift in M-NCS stretching band^{8,9}. The geometry around Ni^{II} remains the same on adduct formation, hence no change in ν_{M-NCS} frequency. The adducts, therefore, possess similar structure as the parent complex $M(NCO)_2Tl_2(SCN)_2$ except that the two ligands are linked to Co^{II} or Ni^{II} in axial position. On the basis of the above results, a polymeric bridged structure can be proposed (Chart 3) for these complexes. The proposed structure is further supported by matching of ligand

M = Co^{II} or Ni^{II}; L = MeOH, dmso, thf, acetone.
Chart 3

with M(II) and Tl(I). Hence, a better match of hard-hard or soft soft can be expected from a high value of the difference (ΔE_{nm}^+) of E_n^+ and E_m^+ as described earlier¹⁰. The ΔE_{nm}^+ values for metal and ligand is higher than those for thallium and ligand (Table 2); so that the ligand will link to M(II) in preference to Tl(I) which are also supported by Person's HSAB principle¹¹.

TABLE 2-CALCULATED QUANTITATIVE SOFTNESS VALUES AND SOFTNESS DIFFERENCE OF METALS AND LIGANDS

Ligands (L)	E_m^+	ΔE_{nm}^+	ΔE_{nm}^+
	of ligands	(Co-L)/(Ni-L)*	(Tl-L)**
py	11.75	11.08/11.59	9.6
nia	13.90	13.23/13.74	11.75
bipy	11.70	11.03/11.54	9.55
phen	11.98	11.21/11.82	9.83
dmso	10.86	10.21/10.70	8.71
thf	11.69	10.02/11.53	9.54

E_n^+ value of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Tl^I taken as -0.67, -0.16 and -2.15, respectively.

* Softness difference, when ligands are attached to Co^{II} or Ni^{II}. ** Softness difference, when ligand are attached to Tl^I.

Ionic complexes: $[M(L)_x][Tl(SCN)(NCO)]_2$; where M is Co^{II} or Ni^{II}; x is 6 for L=py, nia, and 3 for L=phen, bipy: The molar conductance values (Table 1) indicate that these complexes are 1:2 electrolytes. The analytical data show that three

molecules of bipy and phen, and six molecules of py and nia react with each molecule of the Lewis acid. The colour, magnetic moment and electronic spectral band positions show that M(II) has a octahedral geometry in these complexes. The ir band due to thiocyanate groups indicates the presence of S-bonded thiocyanate group¹². The positions of ν_{ON} , ν_{OO} and δ_{NCO} bands at 2210-2180, 1365-1335 and 665-650 cm⁻¹, respectively, due to cyanate group, indicate the presence of N-bonded terminal cyanate group^{1,4,8}. The M-NCS band is absent in these complexes. The higher Dq values in the complexes may be due to the existences of cation of the type $[M(L-L)_3]^{2+}$ or $[M(L)_6]^{2+}$. The difference in the Dq values is due to the different in the moiety around M(II). In polymeric complexes the moieties are $(L)_2M(NCO)_2(NCS)_2$, and in bipyridyl complexes moieties are $[M(bipy)_3]^{2+}$. On account of this difference the Dq values of these complexes of the two series differ. The above results indicate that the ligands are coordinated to metal ion forming the possible cation. Further, the ligand shows the features of coordination through ring-nitrogen. The presence of ν_{M-L} at 240-265 cm⁻¹ also supports this view. The possible anion, therefore, is $[Tl(SCN)(NCO)]_2^-$, because the ir spectra indicate the presence of S-bonded thiocyanate and N-bonded terminal cyanate groups. On the basis of these results, we may propose the following structure for these complexes as

The proposed structures are tentative since single crystal could not be grown.

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